

STUDIES ON THE ADSORPTION FROM NON-AQUEOUS SOLVENTS. PART III

BY A. C. CHATTERJI AND R. D. SRIVASTAVA

Adsorption of two more solutes—cinnamic acid (polar) and phenanthrene (non-polar), in both polar and non-polar solvents has been studied. The changes in the amounts adsorbed from different solvents have been explained on the basis of differences in the internal pressures of solute and solvent. It has been observed that since in a solution consisting of two components, where exists a difference in the internal pressure, the escaping tendencies change, and hence, adsorption also changes. The change increases with the difference and may be positive or negative. It is positive when the solute has a lower internal pressure than the solvent, and negative, when higher. Deviations from the rule occur due to polarity. The adsorption of naphthalene, phenanthrene, benzoic acid and cinnamic acid increases with the increase in the difference, in the solvents having higher internal pressures. But the increase is less marked in acids due to their polarity. The adsorption of naphthalene and phenanthrene decreases with the increase in the difference, in the solvents having a lower internal pressure, but of acids under the same conditions increases, which has been explained due to their polarity.

In previous communications (*this Journal*, 1951, 28, 315 ; 1952, 29, 327) adsorption of polar and non-polar substances from both types of solvents was studied, and the changes in the adsorption from solvent to solvent were accounted for on the basis of changes in the polarity, solubility, surface tension, and the effect of the latter on solubility. In the present paper work has been extended to more solutes, and the changes in the adsorption has been explained on the basis of differences in the internal pressures.

It is known that the internal pressure of a substance is a measure of the attractive force between the molecules. If accumulation in an interface is considered as a manifestation of the escaping tendency of the solute from the solution phase, then with the difference in the internal pressures adsorption will also change as the escaping tendency changes. The substance having a greater escaping tendency will tend to be adsorbed to a greater extent which will be subsequently determined by the difference in the internal pressures.

Taking this point into consideration, an attempt has been made in this paper to correlate the changes in adsorption from different solvents with the differences in the internal pressures.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the chemicals used herein were purified by standard methods. Experimental method was the same as given in Parts I and II of the series (*loc. cit.*). The values of adsorption at one concentration are given in Table I and at other concentrations in Tables II and III. The adsorbed amounts of benzoic acid and naphthalene obtained from the previous work (*loc. cit.*) have also been included for showing the validity of the relationship in these cases also. The values of internal pressures from solubility data have been reproduced in column 2 from Mortimer (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 45, 633). In column 3, calculated values of relative internal pressures from heat of vaporisation

and molecular volumes of liquids are given using Hildebrand's equation (*ibid.* 1919, 41, 1067).

TABLE I

Solvent.	Relative internal pressure.		Adsorption in m. moles/litre at concentration of			
			Naphthalene. (0.2 M)	Phenanthrene (0.5 M)	Benzoic acid. (0.5 M)	Cinnamic acid. (0.5 M)
1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7.
CCl ₄	0.84	0.847	9.30	23.0	103.3	80.2
C ₆ H ₅ CH ₃	0.93	0.875	12.10	26.7	53.7*	70.0
C ₆ H ₆	0.94	0.936	15.5	31.0	66.9	68.2
C ₆ H ₅ Cl	0.98	0.986	9.6*	40.5	38.0	58.0
CH ₃ COCH ₃	1.32	1.030	27.6	44.0	42.3	30.9
CH ₃ COOH	1.95	1.044	21.2	47.2	—	—
<i>n</i> -BuOH	—	1.046	28.2	47.2	49.6	38.0
<i>n</i> -PrOH	—	1.210	31.1	55.0	49.8	39.7
EtOH	2.90	1.423	41.7	58.9	51.0	42.0
MeOH	3.35	1.940	45.6	64.7	51.3	45.6
Naphthalene	1.00	1.000	—	—	—	—
Benzoic acid	1.38	1.010	—	—	—	—
Phenanthrene	1.02	1.006	—	—	—	—
Cinnamic acid	—	0.994	—	—	—	—

*Are irregularities.

TABLE II

Temp. = 30°

Solvent.	Adsorption of phenanthrene in m. moles/litre at concentration							
	0.7M.	0.6M.	0.5M.	0.4M.	0.3M.	0.2M.	0.1M.	0.05M
CCl ₄	26.7	24.9	23.0	21.1	19.0	17.1	14.9	12.1
C ₆ H ₅ CH ₃	31.5	29.1	26.7	24.0	21.5	18.9	16.2	12.3
C ₆ H ₆	36.6	34.0	31.0	28.1	25.0	21.8	18.0	13.2
C ₆ H ₅ Cl	48.1	44.8	40.5	36.0	31.1	26.1	21.0	15.2
CH ₃ COCH ₃	53.2	49.0	44.0	39.1	34.0	29.0	22.8	17.0
CH ₃ COOH	56.0	51.9	47.2	42.0	36.2	30.3	24.0	17.0
<i>n</i> -BuOH	59.9	55.8	51.3	46.5	41.0	35.0	27.7	19.0
<i>n</i> -PrOH	63.1	59.0	55.0	50.8	44.8	37.5	29.0	19.0
EtOH	65.3	62.1	58.9	54.0	47.9	40.7	32.0	22.0
MeOH	74.1	70.0	64.7	59.0	52.2	42.5	33.5	23.0

TABLE III

Temp. = 30°

Solvent.	Adsorption of cinnamic acid in m moles/litre at concentration						
	0.6 M.	0.5 M.	0.4 M.	0.3 M.	0.2 M.	0.1 M.	0.05 M.
CCl ₄	—	80.2	71.4	60.4	46.1	27.4	10.9
C ₆ H ₆ CH ₃	79.8	71.0	61.9	51.4	38.2	21.2	10.1
C ₆ H ₆	76.1	68.2	59.0	49.0	36.6	21.2	10.1
C ₆ H ₅ Cl	64.6	58.0	50.8	41.7	31.6	18.9	9.4
MeOH	51.1	45.6	38.9	31.3	23.1	13.1	9.0
EtOH	47.6	42.0	35.8	29.3	22.2	12.9	9.0
<i>n</i> -PrOH	43.5	39.7	34.3	28.2	21.0	12.8	9.0
<i>n</i> -BuOH	42.0	38.0	33.0	27.1	21.0	12.6	9.0
CH ₃ COCH ₃	32.2	30.9	28.7	24.9	20.0	13.5	9.5

DISCUSSION

Consider a mixture of two components A and B: if the forces between molecules of A are almost the same as those between molecules of B, and neither type of molecule has any polarity resulting in an external electric field, then the forces between A and B will also be the same. Under these conditions the average force acting on any molecule will be independent of composition, and escaping tendency will be normal, hence adsorption will also be normal. From Table I it is seen that the adsorption of all the substances is approaching the normal value in those solvents which have nearly the same internal pressure as the solute.

If, on the other hand, the forces between the molecules of A are greater than those between the molecules of B, the former will tend to aggregate together so that the latter are squeezed out; in other words, the high internal pressure of one of the components of the mixture increases the escaping tendency of the other, and hence, adsorption. For the same reason adsorption of naphthalene and phenanthrene, benzoic and cinnamic acid increases with the increase in the difference of internal pressure in the solvents which have a higher internal pressure than these solutes. The decrease in the adsorption of naphthalene and phenanthrene in the solvents of low internal pressure is also due to the same reason, because in these cases escaping tendency of the solvents is increased as they have a lower internal pressure.

If the component A is polar, that is, it has an unsymmetrical field of force and contains a grouping possessing an appreciable dipole moment, then there is a specific attraction between the molecules which tends to decrease their external electrostatic field. Under these conditions the escaping tendency of a polar compound in non-polar solvents is increased more than that indicated by the direct proportionality to the

differences in the internal pressure. For this reason adsorption of benzoic and cinnamic acids increases in non-polar solvents.

In the extreme case of attraction between both polar molecules, attraction between A and B becomes abnormally large, and hence, in such cases escaping tendencies and adsorption of each species are more reduced than that indicated by the difference in the internal pressure and therefore, increase is not very much marked in the adsorption of acids from polar solvents.

Authors' thanks are due to the Lucknow University for giving facilities for work.

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
LUCKNOW UNIVERSITY
LUCKNOW.

Received October 23, 1952.